

PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPING ENTREPRENEURSHIP TO IMPROVE LIVING STANDARDS IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN: INSIGHTS FROM GLOBAL PRACTICES

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Abstract

This article explores the impact of entrepreneurship on living standards in both developed (USA and Germany) and developing (India and Indonesia) countries, highlighting the critical role of supportive ecosystems. Through examining various national strategies to promote entrepreneurship, such as government policies and access to finance, it demonstrates how entrepreneurship contributes to economic growth and improved living standards. The insights provide valuable guidance for countries like Uzbekistan in leveraging entrepreneurship for sustainable development.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, living standards, economic growth, supportive ecosystem.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is undergoing a transformative era, marked by significant economic reforms and a renewed focus on enhancing the quality of life for its citizens. Central to this transformation is the development of entrepreneurship, recognized globally as a vital engine for economic growth, innovation, and social progress. In the new Uzbekistan, fostering a vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem is not just about stimulating economic diversification and creating jobs; it's about laying the foundation for sustainable development that directly improves living standards across the nation.

The government of Uzbekistan has initiated a series of reforms aimed at liberalizing the economy, improving the business climate, and encouraging the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). These reforms include easing regulatory requirements, simplifying tax codes, and enhancing access to finance for entrepreneurs. Such measures are designed to unleash the potential of the private sector as a driver of economic growth and a contributor to improving the overall quality of life.

However, the way towards developing a robust entrepreneurial ecosystem that can significantly impact living standards involves navigating through a complex landscape of challenges and opportunities. It requires a deep understanding of the current state of entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, including the sectors that hold the most promise for growth and the barriers that aspiring entrepreneurs face.

Foreign Experiences on the Impact of Entrepreneurship on Living Standards

Developed Countries: USA and Germany

USA: In the United States, entrepreneurship is a major driver of economic growth and a key factor in improving living standards. The entrepreneurial ecosystem in the USA is supported by a combination of factors including access to venture capital, a culture of innovation, and robust legal protections for intellectual property. Studies have shown that startups and small businesses play a crucial role in creating jobs, driving innovation, and enhancing the competitiveness of the economy (Shanimon, Vijayan, & Indurajani, 2020). The success of Silicon Valley as a global tech entrepreneurship hub underscores the potential of entrepreneurship to transform economies and improve living standards.

Germany: Germany's Mittelstand, a segment of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), exemplifies how entrepreneurship can contribute to economic stability and high living standards. These enterprises are often family-owned and operate in niche markets, contributing significantly to employment, innovation, and export strength. The German government supports these enterprises through favorable tax policies, financing assistance, and investment in vocational education, demonstrating the role of policy in fostering entrepreneurship and improving living standards (Lokhande, 2015).

Developing Countries: India and Indonesia

India: Entrepreneurship in India has been recognized as a key to addressing unemployment and enhancing living standards, especially among the differently-abled population. The Indian government has implemented various schemes to promote entrepreneurship, such as the Startup India initiative, which aims to build a strong ecosystem for nurturing innovation and startups. Entrepreneurship is seen as a tool for not only creating jobs but also for promoting social inclusion and economic empowerment (Shanimon, Vijayan, & Indurajani, 2020).

Indonesia: In Indonesia, entrepreneurship, particularly among the youth and women, is being promoted as a way to achieve economic independence and improve living standards. The Indonesian government has launched various programs to support SMEs, including access to financing and training. The Pesantren Entrepreneurship program, for example, integrates entrepreneurial education in Islamic boarding schools, aiming to cultivate a new generation of

entrepreneurs who can contribute to economic development and social change (Afidah, 1000).

The experiences of both developed and developing countries illustrate the significant impact of entrepreneurship on improving living standards. While the contexts and specific challenges may vary, the importance of a supportive ecosystem, including access to finance, education, and government policy, is a common theme. These examples provide valuable insights for Uzbekistan as it seeks to harness entrepreneurship for economic development and improved living standards.

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